

Halogenation XII.¹ Derivatives of Carbamic Esters. Chlorine as a Simultaneous Oxidising and Chlorinating Agent.

Part II.

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It has been shewn² in a previous communication that urethanes condense with alcohols under the action of chlorine to form diurethanes, the alcohol being oxidised to the corresponding aldehyde. In the present paper, further cases have been studied.

*iso*Propylurethane condenses with methyl alcohol under the influence of chlorine to form methylene dicarbamic*iso*propyl ester, $\text{CH}_2(\text{NH}\cdot\text{COOC}_3\text{H}_7)_2$. In the case of condensation of the different urethanes with benzyl alcohol a peculiar behaviour is noticed. With aliphatic urethanes the benzyl radical remains intact while in the case of heavily substituted urethanes such as phenyl- and naphthyl-urethanes, the phenyl group is detached and the methylene radical forms the diurethanes. Methyl urethane, *n*-propyl urthane, *isopropyl* urethane, *isobutyl* urethane give rise to benzylidene dimethylurethane, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}(\text{NHCOOCH}_3)_2$, benzylidene di-*n*-propyl urethane, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}(\text{NHCOOC}_3\text{H}_7)_2$, benzylidene

¹ Previous communications on the subject, *Trans. Chem. Soc.*, 101 (1912), 166; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 34 (1912), 1613; 35 (1913), 1044, 1183; 36 (1914) 389, 1007, 1011, 1014; 37 (1915), 567, 569, 578; 38 (1916), 1079, 1809, 1813, 2339, 2546; 39 (1917); 435, 441, 41 (1919), 287, 292, 2028; 43 (1921), 303; 44 (1922), 1538; 45 (1923), 490.

² Datta and Chatterjee, *J. Amer. Soc.*, 44 (1922), 1538.

diisopropyl urethane, $C_6H_5CH(NHCOOC_3H_7)_2$ and benzylidene diisobutyl urethane, $C_6H_5CH(NHCOOC_4H_9)_2$ respectively.

By the action of chlorine on benzyl alcoholic solutions of phenyl- and naphthyl-urethanes, methylene di-*p*-chlorodiphenyl-diurethane, $CH_2(C_6H_4ClNOOC_2H_5)_2$ and methylene di-tetrachloro- α -naphthyl-diurethane,

respectively are produced, the phenyl radical being detached in both the cases. The same products are formed by the action of chlorine on methyl alcoholic solutions of the respective urethanes.¹

EXPERIMENTAL.

Action of Chlorine on iso-Propyl Urethane in Methyl Alcoholic Solution. Methylene-dicarbamic isopropyl Ester, $CH_2 \cdot (NH \cdot CHOOC_3H_7)_2$.

5 grams. of isopropyl urethane are dissolved in 8 c.c. of methyl alcohol and chlorinated for some time when a white solid makes its appearance. During the process the solution becomes hot and white fumes are evolved. The product on evaporation on the water-bath deposits a white solid. This is freed from adhering mother-liquor by suction, recrystallised from dilute alcohol and obtained as white silky needles melting at 110°.

Found: N=13.07. $C_9H_{13}O_4N_2$ requires N=12.84 per cent.

Action of Chlorine on Methyl Urethane in Benzyl Alcoholic Solution. Benzylidenedimethylurethane, $CH_2CH \cdot (NHCOOCH_3)_2$

5 grms. of methyl urethane are added to 8 grms. of benzyl alcohol and chloroform is added till a complete

¹ *loc. cit.*

solution is obtained. A current of chlorine is passed for about half-an-hour when the solution turns yellow and white fumes are evolved with the formation of white granular particles. The solution is next poured in a crystallising dish, cooled in a freezing mixture and placed in vacuum desiccator when the whole thing solidifies. The solid is freed from adhering mother-liquor by suction and pressing on the porous plate, recrystallised from benzene and obtained as white needle-shaped light crystals melting at 175° .

Found: $N=12.14$. $C_{11}H_{14}O_4N_2$ requires 11.76 per cent.

Benzylidene-di-n-propyl-urethane, $C_6H_5CH(NHCOOC_3H_7)_2$ melting at 146.7° (Found: $N=9.99$. $C_{15}H_{22}O_4N_2$ requires $N=9.52$ per cent.) *Benzylidene-di-iso-propyl-urethane*, $C_6H_5CH(NHCOOC_3H_7)_2$ melting at 148° (Found: $N=9.52$ per cent.) and *Benzylidene-di-isobutyl-urethane*, $C_6H_5CH(NHCOOC_4H_9)_2$ (Found: $N=8.89$. $C_{17}H_{26}O_4N_2$ requires $N=8.7$ per cent.) were obtained in a similar way from dipropyl-urethane, di-isopropyl-urethane and di-isobutyl-urethane respectively when dissolved in benzyl alcohol and chloroform and treated with chlorine.

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